

Prevalence of Gypsy Moth in South Korea Due to Climate Change

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Abstract

South Korea has experienced the warmest winter temperature last winter, since the observation began in 1973, recording 3.1 degree Celsius nationwide (From December 2019 to February 2020). During the last two or three years, the area damaged by gypsy moths has been expanding, which is assumed to be related to the temperature rise in the winter. Since the climate in the country is changing into a subtropical climate zone, scientists are expecting increased frequency of new harmful insects approaching and following damages to the environment. The damage due to gypsy moth, to be specific, was known to be severe among the forest areas. To prevent new potential damages in the future, it is keenly required to carry out the more comprehensive study about the relationship between climate change and increased occurrences of pests.

1. Introduction

¹Korea's average annual temperature has risen 1.7 °C for last 100 years (1912~2008), which is noticeably higher than the global average temperature rise (0.74 ± 0.03 °C / 100 years).

The climate change moved Korea into the subtropical climate zone, which outstandingly brought up ecosystem change that tropical fruits such as bananas and pineapples that are known to be cultivated in the subtropical climate zone could be harvested in the southern area of Korea.

Experts anticipate that the outbreak of harmful insects such as gypsy moth and fall armyworm would more frequently occur as the climate change is intensified.

Dr. Jong-Kyun PARK, a Professor of Ecology and Environment Science College of the KyungBuk National University of Korea emphasizes that the countermeasures against the pest outbreaks should be prepared, which would appear more frequently in the future.

Outbreak becomes the universal phenomenon. According to ²the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), as of August 26th 2020, 42 million people are in food crisis due to vast swarm of locusts, which have burned to the ground globally - Yemen, Pakistan as well as African countries such as Ethiopia, South Sudan, and finally advanced northward up to China's Yunnan Province last July.

Experts represented their views that one of main causes for a vast swam of locusts to be rampant is “climate change.” It has been caused by the temperature difference of sea surface between the east and west parts of Indian

¹ "The Climate Change in Korea", Korea Adaptation Center for Climate Change
https://kacc.kei.re.kr/portal/climateChange/changepheno/changepheno_view.do?num=2

² “Desert Locust Crisis”, FAO(Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations)
<http://www.fao.org/emergencies/crisis/desertlocust/en/>

Oceans, in addition to the fact that the high temperature and humidity produced by severely pouring rainfalls last autumn in the East Africa compared to previous years created the optimal habitat conditions. Ultimately, the counterattack of the climate change brings out the apocalypse which transcends the borders.

Meanwhile, Korea has experienced a vast swarm of gipsy moth caterpillar in nationwide including Seoul, Gyeonggi Province and so on in 2020, which scooped leaves of chestnut trees, Chinese plum and oak tree. As winter temperature got warmer, fatality rate of gipsy moths dropped down to 30-40%, which brought up the results that eggs of gipsy moths have hatched explosively.

Additionally, Fall Armyworm, which has scooped all crops including corns in Africa, the Near East, Asia and the Pacific, was first found in Southern parts of Korea such as Cheju Island, Gochang county, and Muahn county. Fall Armyworm is regarded as a harmful insect which threatens the food security of billion people. Therefore, ³FAO has developed a new three-year Global Action for Fall Armyworm Control to ensure a strong coordinated approach at country, regional and global levels. FAO's new global initiative aims to mobilize USD 500 million over 2020-22.

As the analysis data based on the long-term monitoring on the harmful insects outbreak by the climate change were not sufficient in Korea, the damage prediction and prevention research has not carried out actively. To contemplate the importance on current situation, it is firstly required to look into Korean climate change phenomenon in last 100 years and to investigate the outbreak of gipsy moths and concerned damage which has been dispersed rapidly in Korea.

2. Climate Change in Korea

The National Institute of Meteorological Sciences has published a report, or ⁴“Climate Change in 100 Years in Korean Peninsula,” which analyses the trend of climate change in 106 years(from 1912 to 2017) in Korea.

According to the report during last 106 years(from 1912 to 2017), annual average temperature in Korea was 13.2°C (highest annual average was 17.5°C and lowest one was 8.9°C), and annual precipitation was 1237.4mm, while summer got longer by 19 days and winter got shorter by 18 days.

Annual average temperature has increased +0.18°C/10years and annual average daily highest and lowest have increased +0.12°C/10 years, +0.24°C/10 years respectively.

³ Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, <http://www.fao.org/fall-armyworm/global-action/en/>

⁴ "Climate Change in 100 Years in Korean Peninsula ", The National Institute Of Meteorological Sciences http://www.nims.go.kr/?sub_num=969

[Changes in annual average temperature]

Seasonally, the range of temperature increase in last 106 years is high in winter, spring, fall and summer respectively, whose increase was $+0.25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/10\text{ years}$ in Winter, $+0.24\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/10\text{ years}$ in Spring, $+0.16\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/10\text{ years}$ in Fall, and $+0.08\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/10\text{ years}$ in Summer. Additionally, temperature in recent 30 years increased $1.4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ compared to early 20 century (1912~1941), which resulted in the biggest increase of lowest temperature among average temperature, highest temperature and lowest temperature. And additionally, precipitation in recent 30 years has increased by 124mm compared to early 20th century but become more volatile.

Meanwhile, the Korea Meteorological Administration and the Ministry of Environment jointly publish ⁵ "Korea Climate Change Evaluation Report 2020," which forecasts that seasonal average temperature in Korean peninsula would gradually increase around $4.7\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in 2100 compared to 2020, with the forecast on the scenario that greenhouse gas continues to emit at the current level without reduction efforts. On the contrary, if applied the scenario that the greenhouse emission reduction policy would be implemented substantially, seasonal average temperature would increase around average $2.9\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

Additionally, according to the Ministry of Environment which participated into the preparation of this reports, ecologically outbreak of alien species such as Asian predatory wasp (firstly detected in Pusan 2003, having spread into 155 cities and counties) and Ricaniid Planthopper, mosquitoes, or hygienic pests (when temperature rises $+1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ adult population of those pets increase $+27\%$) and mites are expected to rise. Anopheline mosquito has increased four times between 2011 and 2015, while *Aedes albopictus* has went up 3.3 times between 2013 and 2016.

⁵ " Korea Climate Change Evaluation Report 2020 ", http://www.kma.go.kr/notify/press/kma_list.jsp?mode=view&num=1193901

The impact for Climate Change to each disease and insect pest was not evenly applied, though there have been some directions to follow. If the friendly environment including warm winter is gradually made for the harmful insects due to the climate change, the mortality of larva naturally decreased to make insect infestation increased. The phenomenon of rapid increase of gypsy moth population in 2020 which will be addressed in the next chapter easily falls into this context. Furthermore, as an average temperature of spring, fall and winter are expected to rise due to the climate change, it is also forecasted that number of harmful insect increases and duration of their activation expands.

Change of Seasonal Average Temperature and Precipitation in
South Korea

Unit: °C, mm

Year	Average Spring Temperature	Average Summer Temperature	Average Autumn Temperature	Average Winter Temperature
2009-2017	11.21695	23.91849	13.95125	-0.2527483
2018-2050	12.33724	25.02954	15.22681	1.151882
2051-2070	13.72032	26.5279	16.7232	2.902606
2071-2100	15.43706	28.40163	18.82912	4.679151
Year	Average Spring Precipitation	Average Summer Precipitation	Average Autumn Precipitation	Average Winter Precipitation
2009-2017	115.8985	304.518	88.0208	32.53594
2018-2050	113.8254	314.947	93.93651	44.96347
2051-2070	115.1337	356.4433	104.6786	48.07139
2071-2100	130.0588	327.772	94.27228	61.24678

*⁶Source: Korea Rural Economic Institute

3. An Increase of Gypsy moth

Gypsy moth, which exists in the area of South Korea, Japan, the Amur, Siberia, Europe and North America, belongs in classification of Lymantriinae, and nibbles away the leaves of 700~1800cm² until larva becomes pupa to eventually give significant damages to forests and fruits.

Imago develops once a year around July and August and mostly activates during daytime. Eggs are laid as mass in a trunk, which is lower part of tree as many as 300 ones. They pass over the winter and get hatched into larvae in next April. Larvae nibble the leaves for 45 days to 66 days. They usually move around in a group to make sounds of crunching as raindrops, overwhelmingly releasing poos after eating leaves. They live in a colony in the beginning to naturally disperse later. Around from late May to early July they become pupae hanging on between the branches and

⁶ "The Effects of Climate Change on Forest Insect Disturbance in South Korea", Korea Rural Economic Institute (Ahn Hyeon-jin | Lee Sang-min | Choi Jun-yeong) <http://library.krei.re.kr/pyxis-api/1/digital-files/c8808e49-9b26-439c-b93d-2a41f4dfac51>

leaves to become into a moth in 15 days later. Imago may live for 7 to 8 days, whose females lay average 500 eggs to die. Females become too heavy to fly far, instead making males to actively chase females day and night.

*⁷Source: naver.com

*⁸Source : doopedia

According to the Korea Meteorological Administration, last winter(from December 2019 to February 2020) nationwide average temperature reached mildest winter temperature, or 3.1 °C since the first observation began, which naturally made all eggs of gypsy moth hatched rather than being dead.

The report published by Korea Rural Economic Institute in 2018 analyzed that increase of average temperature over four seasons in Korea by the Climate Change made the number of insects as well as the duration of their activation increased. Therefore, the increase of gypsy moth nationwide could be understood in this context.

⁹“As the average spring, autumn, and winter temperatures are likely to increase due to climate change in the future, the insect vector population and active period of insect vectors are expected to increase. The damage rate can increase greatly, in particular, if the climatic factors such as the dry summer and warm winter that are favorable to insect vectors appear simultaneously”

⁷ <https://terms.naver.com/entry.nhn?docId=2429346&cid=46691&categoryId=46691>

⁸ <https://terms.naver.com/entry.nhn?docId=2429346&cid=46691&categoryId=46691>

⁹ "The Effects of Climate Change on Forest Insect Disturbance in South Korea" by Korea Rural Economic Institute
<http://library.krei.re.kr/pyxis-api/1/digital-files/c8808e49-9b26-439c-b93d-2a41f4dfac51>

¹⁰Source: YTN

* ¹¹Source: Yonhapnews

As of June 15th, the area where gypsy moth appeared are 1676ha in Seoul, 1496ha in Kyunggi Province, 1203ha in Kangwon Province, 759ha in Chungbuk Province, 618ha in Incheon respectively, which accounts for 6000ha in total. Larvae of gypsy moth which have a good appetite usually nibble all leaves of broadleaf trees, eventually making all trees bared as seen in winter if the gypsy moth started to spread in the forest. Especially, this year gypsy moth appeared not only in the forest but also penetrated into the urban area.

[¹²Area of Larvae of Gypsy Moth Detected]

Gangwon Province being located in the eastern part of Korea has recently revealed the outbreak status of sporadic pest in major cities and villages, which illustrated that the damage caused by the gypsy moth is dominant over other sporadic pests.

¹⁰ YTN, https://www.ytn.co.kr/ln/0115_202007030725117879

¹¹ Yonhapnews, <https://www.yna.co.kr/view/AKR20200706101200064?section=search>

¹² Nocutnews, <https://www.nocutnews.co.kr/news/5387892>

[¹³Current Status of Sporadic Pests Outbreak (as of June. 12)]

(Unit: ha)

City/Village	Gypsy Moth	Sporadic Pest			
		Total	Spotted lanternfly	Citrus flatid planthopper	Black Planthopper
Total	1,006.0	211.8	170.8	10.2	30.8
Chuncheon	6.3	22.8	14.5	2.0	
Wonju	200	1.0	1.0		
Gangneung		0.2	0.2		
Donghae		32.2	32.2		
Sokcho		2.0			2.0
Samcheok		85.0	85.0		
Hongcheon	55.5				
Hoengseong	589.0	1.9	1.4		0.5
Yeongwol	34.7	1.0	1.0		
Pyeongchang	38.0	5.2	5.2		
Jeongseon	23.8	23.8	3.7		20.1
Cheorwon	24.0	0.2	0.2		
Hwacheon	10.0	10.2	10.2		
Yanggu	16.0				
Inje	8.5	16.0		8.0	8.0
Goseong		1.2	1.2		
Yangyang	0.2	15.4	15.0	0.2	0.2

Meanwhile, referring to American cases, the researches on monitoring the defoliation of gypsy moth have been integrated over long period. In Northeastern area of America during ¹⁴1970 to 2013 defoliation damages by gypsy moth has reached up to 81.0 million cumulative acres.

¹³ Gangwon Provincial Government, <http://gnews.gwd.go.kr/view/doc.html?fn=1592209561846.hwp&rs=/view/html/202009/>

¹⁴ US Forest Service, <https://www.fs.usda.gov/naspf/sites/default/files/naspf/pdf/defoliation1970-2013.pdf>

Gypsy moth is now one of the most destructive insects in the eastern United States. And insects that feed on foliage, including gypsy moths, cause \$868 million in annual damages in the US.

As Korea enters into subtropical climate, it is expected that average temperature during four seasons is continuously increasing and cold winter would disappear. It is anticipated that the occurrence of gypsy moth and the risk of its damages will be drastically accumulated in the future.

In 2020, the damage by gypsy moth was biggest. It is also predictable that the frequent outbreak and possible damage by other sporadic pests such as fall armyworm and walking stick will be increased if the global warming continues. To prevent the issue, it is needed to take the precautionary measures to minimize the pest damages with the international cooperation among nations and regions as well as in-depth researches which are more required than any time.

4. Conclusion

The typical example which explained the rapid increase of sporadic pests as the climate change accelerated in Korean peninsula is “cockroach.” Being called as a living fossil, it seemed to increase in a large scale recently. It is due to the fact the period of pests’ activities have significantly increased, which caused their reproduction time to be accelerated.

CESCO, a comprehensive environment and hygiene company in Korea has conducted a monitoring on Korean sporadic pests last five years, which illustrated that number of cockroaches detected in 2016 was 2,394 thousands, 18% increase compared to 2,026 thousands in 2015. This is as many as 28.5% increase compared to 1,863 thousands, an annual average between 2012 and 2016, and almost 50% increase compared to 1,599 thousands in 2012.

It is observed that the number of cockroaches as well as larvae of gypsy moth which gives severe damage to forests has substantially increased. As global warming is pointed out as one of reasons

for increase of such pests, the attack of insects caused by the climate change in Korea would be around the corner, which forecasts that imagoes being usually coming out once a year might do two or three times a year.

Moreover, the proliferation of pests due to the global warming are not 'sporadic pests' anymore but become 'major pests' in the future, naturally generating the concern that their population continuously increases to become a nuisance. On the contrary the research case has been released that number of beneficial insects has been decreased due the climate change. Researchers in the University of Ottawa in Canada have published the research paper¹⁵ that the correlation of number of frequency of bumble bees' appearance and temperature increase in US and Europe.

In the study, the number of bumble bees in North America and Europe during 2000 and 2014 has decreased 30% in average compared with one during 1901 and 1974. It shows that the number of bumble bees has significantly decreased over anticipation and the annihilation of bumble bees in a large scale has been occurred due to the climate change including hyperthermal phenomenon.

Currently, number of beneficial insects such as bumble bees has been reduced due to the climate change, while the number of harmful insects which transmitted diverse illness to human beings has been rapidly increased. The price of excessive industrial activities by human beings brought out the counterattacks of the nature.

Korean researches remains yet in the stage where the analysis of correlations among environmental factors, simply depends on the short-term monitoring results.

In conclusion, comprehensive analysis on the occurrence, distribution, and characteristics of harmful insects through systematic monitoring should be taken into account. At the same time, the development of research modeling to anticipate the impact of the climate change on the major pests as well as sporadic pests should be carried out continuously.

¹⁵ Science, " Climate change contributes to widespread declines among bumble bees across continents", <https://science.sciencemag.org/content/367/6478/685>